

USING INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION FOR PRE-SCHOOL LEARNERS

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Abstract: Pronunciation is a very important part of mastering any foreign language, including English language. This article analyzes the role of pronunciation in teaching English to pre-school learners and games, activities aimed at developing pronunciation skills.

Keywords: pronunciation, pre-school learners, songs and poems, phonetic games.

When introducing learners to a new word or grammatical material, it is very important to pay attention to its pronunciation. The basis of pronunciation is laid at the initial stage of teaching English. This requires the correct organization of teaching pronunciation in English lessons. It is very important that the chosen methods correspond to the age, level of knowledge and the subject being studied. The following methods can be used to teach English pronunciation for pre-school learners.

Listen and repeat

Imitation is the basis of learning pronunciation. Children imitate pronunciation by listening to live speech that the teacher listens to or with the help of technical means. To make these exercises more interesting, you can use different pictures and movements.

Harmonious couples

These words include words that differ in only one sound and have the same pronunciation, for example: ship-sheep, sit-place, night-right. Using pictures in order to distinguish the pronunciation of such words is also considered very effective. Children learn to pay attention not only to the pronunciation of such words, but also to their meaning.

Songs and poems

Well-chosen songs and poems are also authentic pronunciation sources. Listening to songs and poems from CDs and DVDs and then playing them will bring joy to children. Listening to songs and poems and playing them will greatly help children learn intonation, intonation and accent in their pronunciation.

For example, songs such as "Twinkle, Little Twinkle Star", "Are you Sleeping", will greatly help children improve their pronunciation skills.

Tongue twisters

English Tongue twisters is one of the fun ways to teach children how to pronounce the sounds of the language correctly.

For example: to learn the English sound [p]: - Peter Piper picked a peck of pickled peppers.

[w] - How much wood would a woodchuck chuck if the woodchuck could chuck wood?

[ʃ] - She sells sea shells by the seashore, and the shells she sells by the seashore are sea shells for sure.

[b] - Black background, brown background.

Phonetic games

Phonetic games are designed to correct pronunciation at the stage of forming speech skills and abilities, as well as to gain listening skills. Games can be played in every English lesson. The teacher briefly becomes the leader of the game, and the students become participants. Phonetic games with cards for memorizing English words

1. I hear - I don't hear.

Purpose: the formation of phonemic listening skills.

How to use: students are divided into teams. The teacher pronounces the words.

If he calls a word that has a long vowel ... or ..., the children raise their left hand. If the named word also contains consonants ... or ..., everyone raises both hands. The teacher writes down the mistakes of the players on the board. The team that made the fewest mistakes wins.

2. Wide and narrow vowels.

Purpose: the formation of phonemic listening skills.

How to use: the teacher calls the words. Children raise their hand if the sound is pronounced widely. If the vowel is pronounced narrowly, you cannot raise your hand. The team with the fewest mistakes wins.

3. Right - wrong.

Purpose: the formation of correct phonemic listening skills.

How to use: the teacher names individual words or words in sentences, phrases. The children raise their hand while reading the selected sound in sound combinations. Then he asks each learner in both teams to read certain sound combinations, words, phrases and sentences. If the sound is read correctly, the trainees raise their hand with a green card (flag), if the sound is incorrect, they raise their hand with a red card (flag). The team that, after counting the points, most correctly assesses the presence or absence of errors wins.

4. Who is faster?

Purpose: formation and improvement of the skills of establishing sound-letter correspondences and the meanings of words by ear.

How to use: children are given cards on which the words in a foreign language are given in the first column, their transcription in the second, and the translation of words into Russian in the third. Words in a foreign language are numbered in order. Each learner must, as soon as the teacher pronounces a particular word, put its number next to the corresponding transcription and translation into Russian (or

connect all three correspondences with a continuous line). The winner is the one who quickly and better establishes the correspondence between the foreign word, transcription and translation.

Phonetic games is also suitable to be used as a part of set induction in other lesson to refresh back the samples knowledge in their learning of alphabet or to be used as a teaching aids for the next lesson to keeps strengthening the samples ability in recognizing and distinguishing name and sounds of the letters of the alphabet.

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